

Influence of Curriculum Adaptation and Adoption on Academic Performance of Students with Hearing Impairment in an Inclusive School in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper examined the influence of curriculum adaptation and adoption on the academic performance of secondary school students with hearing impairment in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria. The study adopted the descriptive survey design. The study was conducted in a public secondary school that the Delta State Ministry of Education has designated as an inclusive school in Asaba, Delta State. A simple random sampling technique was used to select fifteen regular teachers who were available during the study, and purposive sampling was used to choose one teacher with a hearing impairment and two professional special education teachers to arrive at 18 teachers as a sample for the study. The instrument for data collection was a checklist titled 'Influence of Curriculum Adaptation and Adoption on Academic Performance of Students with Hearing Impairment (ICAAAPSHI)'. Face validity of the instrument was done by two experts in Special Education and Curriculum Studies, while the reliability of the instrument was tested using Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient to give a reliability index of 0.81. Data was analysed using descriptive statistics of percentages, mean and standard deviation and inferential statistics of the Chi-Square Goodness of fit test. Findings showed, among others, that majority of teachers do not use the various types of curriculum adaptation to influence the academic performance of secondary school students with hearing impairment in inclusive schools in Asaba. It was recommended based on the findings that the Delta State Education Board should step up on external monitoring and supervision of inclusive schools to ensure that teachers use the various types of curriculum adaptation to influence the academic performance of secondary school students with hearing impairment. In addition, school managers in inclusive schools should enhance quality assurance measures that promote curriculum adaptation.

Keywords: Curriculum adaptation and adoption; Academic performance; Students with hearing impairment

Introduction

Curriculum adaptation is a recent terminology that was brought into education approaches to teaching as demanded by the implementation of Education for All (EFA) and inclusive education for students with special needs. It is a teaching practice where teachers adjust the nationally developed curriculum used in regular schools to meet the learning needs of students with special needs. The Nigerian secondary school

curriculum is usually a nationally developed and approved document that contains the courses and the contents of the courses offered by secondary schools. It also encompasses suggested teaching methods, teaching materials, class activities and assessments to ensure teaching and learning takes place. In other words, curriculum refers to what the teacher teaches and what students get to learn (content), its delivery (teaching and learning strategies), evaluation procedures (tests, assignments, quizzes, etc.) and educational resources (charts, videos, textbooks, etc.) that are utilized in classroom teaching to support the attainment of stated teaching and learning objectives (Perner (2004) cited in Mckinney, n.d.). Curriculum can therefore be considered the centrepiece of all school activities to achieve educational goals for all students, including special needs students such as those with hearing impairment (Orhan & Macid, 2014). However, curriculum implementation is key to achieving this goal.

Curriculum implementation is a process that begins when the teacher is handed the developed and approved national curriculum and ends when students have been exposed to the learning experiences prescribed in the document in the classroom. The students are the focus of curriculum implementation because the process is all about helping them acquire knowledge, skills, and relevant behaviours (Edozie, 2016). For instance, in a regular school for regular school students only, the national curriculum is usually adopted and used by teachers to teach all students. While the teacher implements a curriculum in the classroom, the need for curriculum adaptation may arise in order to attend to the learning peculiarities of some students (Ozaji, Unachukwu & Kolo, 2016). Therefore, curriculum implementation and adaptation are largely the teacher's duty. The curriculum used in inclusive schools, where students with diverse learning needs and regular school learners are admitted, has two components: the regular curriculum and the adapted, modified, or differentiated curriculum in advanced nations. However, in most underdeveloped nations, such as Nigeria, some teachers adapt the national curriculum to meet the educational demands of students with special needs in the secondary schools (Onwubolu, 2017).

Adaptation is to make something fit for a specific use; hence, an adapted curriculum is planned to achieve specific learning demands for individuals with special learning needs (Onwubolu, 2013). The use of the three principles of Universal Design Learning (UDL), which are engagement and motivation, representation, and action and expression according to Mckinney (n.d.), was seen as a way of carrying out curriculum adaptation. The first principle is to make learning interesting to engage and motivate students. This is possible through the use of differentiation that involves using a combination of teaching strategies, skills, resources, technology, and classroom tasks that appeal more to the sense of sight to arouse students' interest and maintain their attention while learning. The second principle, representation, is the content of what they are learning, which should be made as physical as possible for students with hearing impairment to see and, touch and make them learn. This also requires that the teacher make learning

possible through the use of appropriate language, like labelling teaching materials and using sign language for the deaf and hard of hearing to enable accessibility to the content of the lesson. The third principle, action and expression, is to provide opportunities for the students to show clearly what they have learned. There is a great need for teachers to support physical interaction with learning materials that will help students demonstrate what they have learnt, such as the use of physical counting aids when teaching mathematics in the nursery and lower basic classes.

Students with hearing impairment have defects in one or more structures of the organ of hearing, the nerve that transfers the sound to the brain and/or the part of the brain that interprets sound (Onwubolu, 2017). Hearing impairment, as found in studies of Biradee (2023) and Onwubolu (2017), has been found to be among the top sensory ailments and is the result of sensorineural and/or conductive malfunctions of the ear. Hearing-impaired students are unable to acquire common knowledge by hearing what goes on around them or what is being spoken through the media. This is to say that they do not have the benefits of accidental learning through hearing that takes place in their environment. They can acquire spoken language but at a slower pace, especially those who desire an oral/aural communication approach. They usually experience impediments in the progression of their language and communication skills when compared to students who can hear (Biradee, 2023).

The use of sign language is another means they acquire language, which usually does not have the same language structure as spoken language or written language. These means of acquiring language pose serious challenges for the students because they expend a lot of energy and effort trying to lip-read and observe body language and facial expressions displayed before they can properly decode messages. Also, using sign language can frustrate some of the students, as they have to depend on looking at the fingers of the person signing all day. The regular school students who do not have to lip-read before they can hear the teacher do not experience the challenges experienced by students with hearing impairment. This brings about the need for curriculum adaptation that aims to fit the students and provide support for learning.

Curriculum adaptation refers to modifications, adjustments and needed changes applied to the learning process, teaching materials and classroom environment to ensure that the learning needs of all students are met, especially the educational needs of students with special needs. This is to say that curriculum adaptation involves making the regular curriculum different to meet the different learning needs of students by adapting the physical classroom environment, sound level, light level, curriculum content, the teaching process, assessment and evaluation to ensure learning takes place by all students and to improve academic performance of students with special needs. Curriculum adaptation for students with hearing

impairment may include student's use of hearing aids, sound amplifier, visual aids, computer-based learning, Sign language (manual communication) for teaching, pre-teaching key concepts, words and terms in a lesson before the main lesson, use of peer tutoring, cooperative groups and much more (Adeniyi, 2022; Ozoji, Unachukwu & Kolo, 2016). Some ways teachers can adapt different curricula to suit students with special learning needs include to adapt the environment, adapt the presentation of lessons, use computer-assisted instruction, total communication, change the pace of lesson presentation, use of varied modes for resources, modify teaching resources, modify assessment, change curriculum and relate with students acceptably.

Freitas, Simoes, Miniero, Rosa and Santos (2023), in a study that investigated how the curriculum of Europeans promotes resilience of communication skills, establishing and nourishing relationships in hearing-impaired children and adolescents, used a sample of 37 children and adolescents with hearing impairment from three regions of Portugal. The instruments for data collection were standardized questionnaires which covered children, adolescents, guardians and teachers. The research procedure included a 90-minute weekly session with each session followed by the application of the resilience curriculum framework with required curriculum adaptations for mindfulness tasks, storytelling, role-playing and use of worksheets. The statistical analysis used to analyze the data collected was the mean scores. Findings revealed that the mean score from pre-test to post-test assessment increased on all the instruments used. The researchers concluded that the use of curriculum adaptation to promote resilience was favourable to children and adolescents with hearing impairment, as it allowed for the emergence of particular skills associated with promoting resilience. The consequence of this was that enhanced quality of life for hearing-impaired children and adolescents was evident.

In addition, Pena, Suarez and Baelo (2016) examined the influence of curricular adaptation shown by hearing-impaired students enrolled at the Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia (UNED). Variables such as degree of satisfaction with the provisions of adaptations, benefits the students perceived in terms of their self-efficacy, provisions of social support in school and reduction in pre-examination anxiety. The sample for the study was 133 students with hearing impairment; 28 were provided with some kind of modification, which represented the majority (84.84%) of the students at UNED who have received one form of modification or the other. The instrument for the study was an online questionnaire designed specifically to collect data for the study. Data analysis was done using inferential statistics, measuring relationships among variables. Results found that the level of satisfaction among students provided with curricular adaptations was high. This implies that there is a significant relationship between the need for adaptations and student satisfaction that influences their academic performance. The greatest perceived

benefit was attained in regard to a drop in the rate of anxiety during examinations, resulting in better academic performance. Moderate benefits were observed as regards confidence and social support.

On the other hand, curriculum adoption is the act of teachers practicing the prescribed national curriculum for secondary schools and using it in the classroom as outlined in the document without any modifications or amendments (Edozie, 2016). In Nigeria, regular classroom teacher training prepares regular teachers to adopt the prescribed national curriculum for secondary schools during implementation. Hence, teachers implement the curriculum by adopting the contents for the class of students they are to teach, adopting the methods of teaching, teaching materials, assessment techniques and evaluation methods in the curriculum. In contrast, special teachers are prepared to adopt and adapt, where necessary, the curriculum to meet the peculiar educational needs of special students. They are also trained to modify by personalising the curriculum and developing an Individual Educational Plan (IEP), which is a personal curriculum for a special child. Literature has shown that curriculum adaptation is effective in improving the educational outcomes of hearing-impaired students but the experience of teachers has also shown that curriculum adoption could influence on all students differently (Freitas, Simoes, Miniero, Rosa & Santos, 2023; Pena, Suarez & Baelo, 2016). However, there appears to be a dearth of studies on the influence of curriculum adaptation and adoption on the academic performance of hearing-impaired students in Delta State.

Statement of the Problem

The implementation of the Education for All (EFA) agenda and inclusive education act demands that if effective teaching and learning should take place, the Nigerian secondary school curriculum, which is a document that encompasses suggested teaching methods, teaching materials, class activities and assessment should be structured in such a way that promotes attending to the needs of special needs students. This implies that curriculum implementation is crucial to achieving such goals, and teachers are the major stakeholders. The curriculum implementation process begins when the developed and approved national curriculum is given to the teacher and ends when students have engaged in classroom interactions that expose them to the prescribed learning experiences stated in the document. However, while in a regular school for regular students only, the national curriculum is usually adopted and used by teachers to teach students, on the other hand, in an inclusive school, which promotes the Education For All (EFA) and inclusive education agenda, the use of curriculum adoption only by teachers cannot suffice. There is a need for teachers to adapt the curriculum in order to meet the educational needs of special students. By implication, the curriculum used in inclusive schools with students with diverse learning needs is slightly different from the one used in regular schools due to adaptation. However, in most underdeveloped nations, such as Nigeria, some teachers are not fully equipped with the knowledge and practice of curriculum adaptation in handling the peculiarities of special needs students in inclusive

schools. This situation, as different studies have found, poses a challenge to the academic performance of special students and calls for practising curriculum adaptation in inclusive schools. This study was therefore carried out to examine the influence of curriculum adaptation and adoption on the academic performance of students with hearing impairment in inclusive schools in Asaba, Delta State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to examine the influence of curriculum adaptation and adoption on the academic performance of hearing-impaired secondary school students in the inclusive school in Asaba, Delta State of Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. What are the types of curriculum adaptation used to influence the academic performance of secondary school students with hearing impairment in an inclusive school in Asaba, Delta State of Nigeria?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant influence of curriculum adaptation on the academic performance of secondary school students with hearing impairment in Delta State of Nigeria.

2. There is no significant influence of curriculum adoption on the academic performance of secondary school students with hearing impairment in Delta State of Nigeria.

Methods

The study employed the descriptive survey design. It was conducted in the only public secondary school (Government Model Secondary School) in Asaba, designated by the Delta State Ministry of Education for both hearing and hearing-impaired students. Simple random sampling technique was used to select fifteen regular teachers, and purposive sampling was used to select one teacher with a hearing impairment and two professional special education teachers to arrive at eighteen teachers as the study's sample size.

The instrument for data collection was a 22-item structured questionnaire titled 'Influence of Curriculum Adaptation and Adoption on Academic Performance of Students with Hearing Impairment Questionnaire (ICAAAPSHIQ)'. Two experts in Special Education and Curriculum carried out the instrument's face validity, while the reliability was conducted using Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient and a Reliability index of 0.81 was obtained. The instrument was rated on a 2-point scale of Used and Not Used which was weighted based on percentages and a 4-point Likert scale of Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree (SD) which was weighted as follows SA (4 points), A (3 points), D (2 points) and SD (1 point). The same weighting applied to the measure on extents, resulting in a mean score average of 2.50 as a decision rule. The instrument was administered to the respondents by the researchers after obtaining permission from the

appropriate authorities, and collected on the spot so as to guarantee a hundred percent rate of return. Data was analyzed using percentages, mean scores, standard deviation and the Chi-Square Goodness of fit test for the hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance.

Results

RQ1: What are the types of curriculum adaptation used to influence the academic performance of secondary school students with hearing impairment in Delta State of Nigeria?

Table 1: Percentage Table on Teachers’ Usage of Types of Curriculum Adaptation to Influence the Academic Performance of Students with Hearing Impairment

S/N	STATEMENTS	USED (%)	NOT USED (%)
1.	I use visual aids while teaching	18 (100%)	0 (0%)
2.	I use Sign Language while teaching	18 (100%)	0 (0%)
3.	I pre-teach key words, terms and new words in the lesson	8 (44%)	10 (56%)
4.	I use peer tutoring	7 (39%)	11 (61%)
5.	Students make use of hearing aids	2 (11%)	16 (89%)
6.	I use Cooperative Learning	8 (44%)	10 (56%)
7.	I adapt assessment to suit the students e.g. the use of visuals	2 (11%)	16 (89%)
8.	I use Sound Amplifier in class	0 (0%)	18 (100%)
9.	I adapt presentation of Lesson	3 (17%)	15 (83%)
10.	I adapt teaching materials	2 (11%)	16 (89%)
	Total %	37.7%	62.3%

Table 1 shows that while 37.7% of respondents agree to the use of various types of curriculum adaptation to influence the academic performance of hearing-impaired secondary school students, 62.3%, on the other hand, agree to its non-usage. This implies that the majority of respondents do not use the various types of curriculum adaptation to influence the academic performance of hearing-impaired secondary school students.

Test of Hypotheses

Ho₁: There is no significant influence of curriculum adaptation on the academic achievement of secondary school students with hearing impairment in Asaba, Delta State.

Table 2: Chi-Square Goodness of fit test on Influence of Curriculum Adaptation on the Academic Achievement of Secondary Students with Hearing Impairment in Delta State

Item	SA	A	D	SD	χ^2	Df	p-value	α	Decision
	OV EV	OV EV	OV EV	OV EV					
11	3	3	6	6	38.710 ^a	15	0.001	0.05	Sig.
	3.2	2.3	5.0	7.5					
12	4	2	6	6					
	3.2	2.3	5.0	7.5					
13	1	2	7	8					
	3.2	2.3	5.0	7.5					
14	2	1	7	8					
	3.2	2.3	5.0	7.5					
15	9	5	2	2					
	3.2	2.3	5.0	7.5					
16	0	1	2	15					
	3.2	2.3	5.0	7.5					
Total	19	14	30	45					
	19.0	14.0	30	5.0					

Table 2 shows the chi-square goodness of fit test on the influence of curriculum adaptation on the academic achievement of secondary school students with hearing impairment in Asaba, Delta State. Here, the responses are broken down into four categories (Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree), with corresponding observed and expected counts for each item. The overall chi-square statistic is 38.710, with 15 degrees of freedom. The associated p-value is 0.001, which is below the 0.05 threshold. This statistically significant result indicates that there is a significant influence of curriculum adaptation on the academic achievement of hearing-impaired students. The distribution of responses across the four categories deviates sufficiently from the expected counts to confirm that how the curriculum is adapted

has a meaningful influence on academic performance. In this context, curriculum adaptation shows a clear, significant influence. This suggests that the process or manner of formally adapting the curriculum is critical to the academic success of hearing-impaired students.

H₀₂: There is no significant influence of curriculum adoption on the academic achievement of secondary school students with hearing impairment

Table 3: Chi-Square Goodness of fit test on Significant Influence of Curriculum Adoption on the Academic Achievement of Secondary Students with Hearing Impairment in Delta State

Item	SA		A		χ^2	Df	p-value	α	Decision
	OV	EV	OV	EV					
17	12	12.7	6	5.3	5.151 ^a	5	0.398	0.05	Not Sig.
18	10	12.7	8	5.3					
19	12	12.7	6	5.3					
20	15	12.7	3	5.3					
21	15	12.7	3	5.3					
22	12	12.7	3	5.3					
Total	76	76.0	32	32.0					

Table 3 shows the chi-square goodness of fit test of the influence of curriculum adoption on the academic achievement of hearing-impaired secondary school students in Asaba, Delta State. For several items, observed scores (OV) and expected values (EV) were recorded, and the overall chi-square statistic was calculated to be 5.151 with 5 degrees of freedom. With a p-value of 0.398, which is well above the conventional significance level of 0.05, the study concluded that there is no statistically significant influence of curriculum adoption on the academic achievement of hearing-impaired secondary school students. In other words, the differences between what was observed and what was expected are not large enough to suggest that adopting the curriculum plays a significant role in influencing academic outcomes for these students. Analysis of data revealed that curriculum adoption does not appear to significantly affect the academic achievement of hearing-impaired students.

Discussion of Findings

This study found that the majority of teachers do not use the various types of curriculum adaptation to influence the academic performance of hearing-impaired secondary school students in inclusive schools in Asaba, Delta State. This finding is in line with Onwubolu (2017), who submitted that the curriculum used in inclusive schools where students with diverse learning needs and regular school learners are admitted has two components: the regular curriculum and the adapted curriculum. However, in most underdeveloped nations, such as Nigeria, not all teachers adapt the national curriculum to meet the educational needs of special students in the secondary schools. The finding reiterates the assertion of Edozie (2016) that the issues of curriculum implementation and adaptation are largely the teacher's duty.

This study also found that there is a consensus among teachers that curriculum adaptation has a high influence on the academic performance of hearing-impaired students in inclusive schools in Asaba, Delta State. That is, there is a significant influence of curriculum adaptation on the academic achievement of hearing-impaired students. This finding aligns with Freitas, Simoes, Minihero, Rosa and Santos (2023), who sampled 37 hearing-impaired children and adolescents from three regions of Portugal and found that the implementation of an adapted curriculum promotes resilience and is beneficial to hearing-impaired children and adolescents. This underscores the point that curriculum adaptation involves consciously making the regular curriculum different to meet the different educational needs of students by adapting the physical classroom environment, sound level, light level, curriculum content, the teaching process, assessment and evaluation to ensure learning takes place by all students and to improve the academic performance of special students.

In addition, the study also found that there is a consensus among teachers that curriculum adoption has a low influence on the academic performance of hearing-impaired students in inclusive schools in Asaba, Delta State. That is, there is no statistically significant influence of curriculum adoption on the academic achievement of hearing-impaired students. This finding aligns with Freitas et al. (2023) and Pena et al. (2016) indicate that teachers' experiences have shown that curriculum adoption could influence all students differently, including both regular students and those with special needs. Edozie (2016) asserted that curriculum adoption is the act of teachers implementing the prescribed national curriculum for secondary schools and using it to teach in the classroom, as outlined in the document, without any modifications or amendments. By implication, therefore, when teachers implement the curriculum by adopting the contents for the class of students they are to teach, whether regular or students with special needs, each student will be differently influenced, especially special students, because in contrast, special teachers are prepared to adopt and adapt where necessary the curriculum to achieve the special needs of students with specific educational demands and not just adopt it.

Conclusion

This study sought to find out the influence of curriculum adaptation and adoption on the academic performance of secondary school students with hearing impairment in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria. Despite the finding that the majority of teachers do not use the various types of curriculum adaptation in classroom teaching, there is still a consensus among them that curriculum adaptation **has a high influence** on the academic performance of hearing-impaired students. This implies that there is a gap between theory and implementation. This underscores the point that knowledge of the influence and usage of curriculum adaptation is a separate but intertwined task, and teachers need to be trained and retrained on their points of intersection and its benefits to the academic performance of hearing-impaired students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that:

1. The Delta State Education Board steps up on external monitoring and supervision of inclusive schools to ensure that teachers use the various types of curriculum adaptation to influence the academic performance of hearing-impaired secondary school students.
2. Due to curriculum adaptation having a high influence on academic performance of hearing impaired students, school managers in inclusive schools should enhance quality assurance measures such as adapting the physical classroom environment, sound level, light level, curriculum content, the teaching process, assessment and evaluation that will continuously improve academic performance of special students.
3. The low influence of curriculum adoption underscores the fact that a combination of adaptation and adoption is required in inclusive schools and not just adoption therefore, there is need for training and re-training of both regular and special teachers in inclusive schools on how to adopt and adapt where necessary the curriculum to meet the specific educational demands of special students.

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